

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE

Summary of 2. Symposia with Representatives of R & I Structures

Deliverable 2.3

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EELISA innoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This document has been prepared for the fulfillment of deliverable D 2.3. “Summary of II. Symposia with Representatives of R & I Structures” classified under the second work package of the EELISA Innovation and Common Research Strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA innoCORE) project will be referred to as WP2 – “EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy”.

According to the EELISA-InnoCORE Grant Agreement; two symposia should be organized under the second work package with the following objectives:

- compilation of significant research and development output in the last five years,
- discussion of future directions for strategic research areas,
- other potential activities complying with EELISA education, research, and development objectives,
- identification of thematic research areas of laboratories within partner universities

The first symposia were held in Istanbul on 16 May 2022. The summary report on first symposium was prepared with D 2.2 Deliverable (Summary of I. Symposia with Representatives of R & I Structures”). The symposium, which was held for the second time this year, was again held in Istanbul on 12 July 2023¹ The article on the website relevant to the second symposia can be seen as the link below.

<https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-innocores-symposium-will-take-place-on-july-12th-in-istambul/>

The symposium took place one day before and parallel to the EELISA Governing and Executing Board meetings with the aim of making connections, finding synergies and complementarities, that results from one project can benefit and feed the other.

The main objectives of the second symposia, which was held in Istanbul on 12 July 2023 with the representatives of R & I Structures, can be seen as follows:

- to discuss enabling EELISA Research & Innovation Strategy through EELISA Communities by focusing on the results of D.2.5 deliverable (“Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs”)
- to understand and discuss the EELISA partners industrial Ph.D. practice at their institutions in detail.
- to understand and discuss the EELISA partners industry Chair practice at their institutions in detail.

The symposium was accomplished in three directions. The first part, conducted via workshop in the morning, focused on a more theoretical approach regarding the picture of challenges and scientific technological needs revealed in EELISA Communities. Firstly, workshop participants who represent some EELISA communities used the MIRO Board to reflect their community's contributions in meeting their R&I needs. Secondly, the same participants added their

¹ <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-innocores-symposium-will-take-place-on-july-12th-in-istambul/>

comments on R&I expectations, barriers and obstacles of their communities to the MIRO board. Lastly, they gave some solutions about improvement areas regarding R&I barriers faced by communities and also put some future directions for the second call of EELISA connect workshops.²

In the second and third parts of the symposium, a “Joint Industrial Ph.D. model” and then an “Industrial Chair Approach” panels were accomplished respectively in a fruitful way.

The second innoCORE Symposium Program can be seen as below:

Table 1: The second InnoCORE Symposium Program

08.30-09.30	Registration / Coffee & Snacks
09.00-09.10	Welcome Speech by ITU Rector
09.10-09.20	Speech by Dale Martin, EELISA President
09.20-09.30	Speech about EELISA 2.0 by EELISA Coordinator Alberto Garrido
09.30-09.40	Speech by Sofia Costa D’Aguiar, EELISA Executive Director
09.40-10.15	Concert (Hallway)
10.15-12.00	<p>Workshop-Enabling EELISA Research & Innovation Strategy through EELISA Communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Presentation of the D2.5 Report on challenges revealed in first EELISA (20 min) · Policy Recommendations and Future Directions (80 min) <p>Moderator: Dr. Nihan Yıldırım-Dr. Bersam Sidal Bolat Reporter: Dr. Burcu Bulut</p>
12.00-13.15	Lunch Break
13.15-15.00	<p>Panel 1: Joint Industrial Ph.D. Model (105 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Discussion on Developing Ph.D. thesis financed by industry and co-advised <p>Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Clarisse ANGELIER - Chief Executive Officer of the French National Association for Research and Technology (ANRT) · Dr. Henriette MÜLLER-AHRNDT, Deputy Head of the FAU Graduate Centre · Prof. Calogero ODDO, Professor at SSSA · Sonia ROIG, Coordinator of doctoral programmes at UPM. · Prof. Chiara CAPPELLI, Deputy Rector for Technology Transfer at SNS · László Gergely Vigh – Director for International Academic Affairs, BME <p>Moderator: Dr. Esra Çapanoğlu, ITU Reporter: Dr. Mehmet Akif Yazıcı</p>
15.00-15.15	Coffee Break
15.15-17.00	<p>Panel 2: Industry Chair Approach (105 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Discussion on Industry Chair for developing and executing a high-impact research agenda, developing multi-investigator programs and multi-disciplinary

² <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-first-innocore-joint-call/>

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laboratories, developing innovative training program and curricula, fostering collaborations across the industry and academia.

Panelists:

- Juan Manuel MUÑOZ GUIJOSA, Associate Vice-Rector for Innovation and Technology Transfer- Director of the UPM Technology Transfer Office
- Alexandru MARIN, EU IPR Helpdesk Ambassador Director of the Technology Transfer Office at UPB
- Dr. Vincent SEMETÉY - CNRS Senior researcher at PSL - Head of Urban Mines Chair (ecosystem)
- Dr. Ayşe Aybike Şeker - Senior Lead Engineer at ASELSAN Academy
- Adrián Horváth - Industrial Professor at BME
- László Gergely Vigh – Director for International Academic Affairs, BME

Moderator: Balázs Bokor, BME

Reporter: Dr. Alper Yurttas

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People responsible for EELISA innoCORE R&I Strategy under innoCORE

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions (Alphabetical order)

Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

EELISA ACRI. Advisory Council Research and Innovation

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solving the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven collaboration and working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

HEIs. Higher Education Institutions.

IPR. Intellectual Property Rights.

Industry Chair. Industrial Chair is a prestigious academic position that involves a close partnership between a university or research institution and an industry or a consortium of industrial partners.

Industrial Ph.D.. It is a doctoral programme in which research is carried out in strong collaboration with the industry (sometimes under a co-supervision scheme) where the research results are close to industrial utilization based on pre-drafted IP rights and financing agreements.

R&I. Research and Innovation

RAs. Research Areas

SDGs. Sustainable Development Goals.

SRA. Strategic Research Areas. The research areas selected as “strategic” by the EELISA consortium at the Kick-off meeting.

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1. ENABLING EELISA RESEARCH & INNOVATION STRATEGY THROUGH EELISA COMMUNITIES WORKSHOP

- a) The workshop “Enabling EELISA Research & Innovation Strategy through EELISA Communities” took place on the first day of Symposia 2, July 12, between 10.15-12.00 with the participation of EELISA innoCORE Strategic Representatives and Community representatives. The moderation was performed by Nihan Yıldırım and Bersam Bolat, and reporting was performed by Burcu Bulut from the ITU team.

As defined in the EELISA Communities Platform³ and referred by “D2.5 Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs in EELISA innoCORE” report, “The EELISA communities are mission-driven collaboration and working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.”

“D2.5 Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs” has been an Input to the Workshop and provided discussion guidelines.

The workshop agenda included the following steps:

1- Presentation on D2.5 Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs in EELISA innoCORE

- a. Role and Importance of D2.5 Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs in EELISA innoCORE
- b. Methodology and Rationale
- c. Dimensional Analysis of EELISA Communities and Activities
 - i. Challenges by SDGs
 - ii. Scientific and technological needs identified by SRAs

b) Community Survey Findings

2) Discussion on the findings of D2.5 with participants

3) Thoughts on the Policy Recommendations and Future Directions based on the findings and discussions from steps (1) and (2).

The participation from the following 5 communities provided the inclusivity of the workshop. It strengthened the potential of the workshop to reveal insights on the actual, real-world practices of the communities and offer a multi-disciplinary view of the EELISA Communities’ linkages with the R&I dimensions of EELISA.

- CIRCULAR Community ⁴

³ Detailed information about the EELISA Communities are available at <https://community.eelisa.eu/> and https://eelisa.eu/eelisa_communities_activities/

⁴ <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/circular-eelisa-community/>

- Open Science Community ⁵
- SSERIES ⁶
- The Egalitarian Societies ⁷

The approach towards defining the portfolio of challenges revealed in EELISA communities had been based on the combination of the (a) societal challenges listed by Communities as the topics to be responded to by them, (b) technological needs, and (c) scientific needs which EELISA Communities focus on overcoming these societal challenges, as schematized in Figure 1:

Figure 1: The approach towards defining the portfolio of challenges revealed in EELISA communities.

The Miro Board that was designed and used in the Workshop is shown in the following Figure:

⁵ <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/open-science-community/>

⁶ <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/sseries-science-for-a-sustainable-envision-of-reality-and-information-for-an-engaged-society/>

⁷ <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/egalitarian-societies-opportunities-for-everyone-es-o4e/>

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1st Section of the Workshop- Miro Board Practice:

In the first section of the workshop practice, the participants are given 30 minutes for individual work to reflect their ideas to the Miro Board. In this board, columns showed the topics discussed in the workshop. Part I is excluded as it was the presentation made by the ITU team. Part II includes a discussion of the findings from D2. 5 report. PART II.1 is the “Challenges Revealed in Communities”, and the “Scientific Technological Needs Revealed in Communities”. PART II.2 is the “Communities’ contribution to their members’ in meeting R&I and Education needs for overcoming barriers/obstacles”. PART II.3 is the “Expectations and Needs, Barriers and Obstacles of Communities”. These dimensions are handled in 2 pillars as shown in the rows of the board: The first pillar is the findings from the D2.5 report, for presenting the “reported knowns”, and the second pillar is the “recommended / to be raised insights” expected from the discussions and views of the participants of the workshop.

Based on this structure, the recommended/raised issues from the participants have been as follows. In this list “C” indicates the input is provided by the Community Representative and “S” shows the Strategic Representatives from EELISA innoCORE Project team:

PART II.1 Challenges Identified in Communities

- Calls should be planned in advance, with clear criteria for participation and guidelines on how the funding can be allocated. (JGN) C.1.
- The dualism between communities and clusters does not clearly define the role of communities in R&I. C.2.
- Encouraging partners to attend events in person. C.3.
- What actions will we take to increase participation in underrepresented SDGs, such as no poverty and zero hunger? C.4.
- The budget for additional calls should be clearly stated since these calls are vital for the sustainability of communities. Without them, communities would struggle to thrive. C.1.
- Greater involvement of professors at events is needed. C.3.
- Implementing mechanisms to reward and incentivize participation can be beneficial in encouraging community members to engage in the calls actively. S.3.

Operational Requirements for leading to the Identification of the Scientific and Technological Needs

- Promote research collaborations, participation in calls for proposals (even if not necessarily for research), etc., it would be necessary to map research topics, interests, and problems comprehensively. S.3.
- Organize meetings to exchange ideas, share projects for activities, etc., to identify and involve new partners. S.3.
- Establish joint degree/master/Ph.D. programs or intensive blended programs to facilitate student participation in the activities. S.3.

PART II.2. Communities' Contributions to Meeting R&I and Education Needs and Overcoming Barriers/Obstacles

JGN, CIRCULAR Community

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- The EELISA Connect workshops must be continuous: the results already achieved in the initial meetings need continued support for the development of current proposals leading up to their presentation. S.5.
- There's a significant issue concerning the participation of several EELISA partners: while half of the universities are highly active, the other half rarely participate in any events, despite available facilities and financial assistance. Why? Is it due to a lack of information? Excessive workload? A lack of enthusiasm or interest in the Alliance? C.3.
- Increased interaction between universities at the community level is imperative, going beyond the relations of those responsible for EELISA. C.3.
- SSERIES has bolstered the participation of some members in the two joint calls, introducing new activities (e.g., Research-Based approaches) and enhancing the implementation of challenge-based learning approaches in UPM courses (UPM call). They also established a Citizen Lab where any interested participant can propose challenges to be collaboratively solved. S.3.
- Open Science Community: The BLOOM-OS Bootcamp will enhance the open science skills of early-career researchers. Hopefully, it can become an annual event. S.3.
- The Egalitarian Societies Community hosts significant events connecting engineering with diversity and inequalities. S.4.

PART II.3. Expectations and Needs, Barriers or Obstacles of Communities

- Pay attention to the deliverables of WP4 of EELISA Project; there may be some overlaps. C.2.
- JGN, CIRCULAR Community: Assist in connecting professors and researchers with shared interests from other partner universities. S.3.
- Expectation: Integrating community activities directly into the curriculum by incorporating a community activity into a course program. S.3. Barriers: Low interconnectedness between researchers and a lack of incentives, resulting in a lack of motivation to build a community. C.3.
- Expectation: There should be a common mechanism or organizational structure for each EELISA community to handle administrative work (reporting, organizing joint meetings with member groups, etc.). Currently, there are coordinators for this (with unclear responsibilities), but having a structured approach to support student work and partner efforts is crucial for sustainability. S.2.
- Since finding time for activities involving students is challenging, it would be beneficial to designate one common week per semester free of other academic commitments dedicated to EELISA activities. This could also leverage the Athens Alliance (<http://athensnetwork.eu/network-list.html>). S.3.
- Barrier & Expectation: The increasing number of events reduces interest in them. An online calendar of public events can assist organizers in scheduling events at optimal times. S.3.
- We are planning a joint event with the ATHENS network. The ATHENS event will also be open to the EELISA Sustainable BCC Community.
- Enrollment of students is challenging, communication issues persist, and there are sometimes delays that are too short. C.3.

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2nd Section of the Workshop: Discussion and Wrap Up Session

After the Miro Board is filled with the sticky notes of the participants in the above given 3 topics, in the second section of the workshop, the participants firstly discussed the Improvement Areas, as listed below:

Improvement Areas for EELISA's Support in Effective Research & Addressing R&I Barriers

- **UPM (InnoCORE):** InnoCORE is currently developing and testing tools and instruments to enhance research collaborations. This includes an open call for workshops, a future networking platform, and a catalog of infrastructures. It would be highly beneficial to receive feedback from communities regarding the effectiveness of these tools, how they could be improved, and how they might be tailored to meet community needs better. S.3.
- **UPM (InnoCORE):** Communication and engagement with researchers remain challenging. Sometimes, there are sufficient funds to support travel, but engaging researchers or staff is not always straightforward. For example, consider the Circular Models workshop (this is related to Part II.1: Challenges revealed in communities, answer: "Encouraging partners to participate in events in person"). C.3.

Wrap-Up Session

In the Wrap Up Session, the moderator of the workshop (Nihan Yıldırım) and the reporter of the session (Burcu Bulut) combined and consolidated the inputs/statements of the participants from Part II and Discussion sessions in Sticky Notes (in Purple color in the Miro Board) which had been the raw clusters of participant ideas.

First Cluster - Sticky Note -1 : Revealed needs

- Ensuring transparency in EELISA processes
- Engaging staff, researchers (professors), and students.
 - **Solution (1):** Providing students with ample time to prepare for participating in events.
 - **Solution (2):** Supporting in-person participation by aligning academic calendars with EELISA activity calendars.
 - **Solution (3):** Analyzing and addressing the limited participation of students and professors in activities.
 - **Solution (4):** Early notification.
- Addressing the invisibility of incentives for senior members (What motivates participation in an EELISA community? Refer to motivation patterns).
- Requiring multiple scientific and technical approaches.
- Defining actions to expand the coverage of communities through SRAs and SDGs.

Second Cluster - Sticky Note - 2: Problems

- How communities will contribute to the clusters. Communities are Problem finders (with a broad mission); Clusters are Problem solvers (thematic).

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- Motivation Patterns of Communities:
 - A more extensive network and access to more resources.
 - Self-motivation.
 - However, we must move beyond self-motivation towards solid motivation and incentives, considering that self-motivation alone may apply to a minority.
- Lack of an EELISA online event/activity calendar.
- Are the institutions within the community communicating sufficiently with each other?
- Exploring any other institutional barriers not mentioned that affect community effectiveness (highlighting the importance of event participation, e.g., how it impacts a participant's badge).
- Clarifying credentials for institutions and students ensures alignment with their current grading systems.
- Establishing connections between EELISA researchers working in the same areas; creating platforms and tools for researchers to contact each other.
- The lack of communication about events affects the number of participants, especially the engagement of separated activities/meetings under SRAs through the participation of young researchers (ECRs), which supports a bottom-up approach.
- While some solutions/tools have been proposed, they are currently insufficient and warrant in-depth discussion.

Third Cluster - Sticky Note 3: External Linkages

- Discussing collaboration with other alliances and networks (building linkages with other networks) is essential. However, assessing our existing connections and determining our specific needs is vital.

As a result of the workshop practice, the combined and synthesized findings from the Workshop have been reported as listed in Table 1 in the Wrap Session, regarding the challenges of EELISA Communities on “Enabling EELISA R&I Strategy.”

Table 2: Challenges and Proposed Solutions (Improvement areas) of EELISA Communities in Enabling EELISA R&I Strategy

Issues - Dimensions	Challenges	Solutions
C.1.Financial	Joint calls: Clear criteria of participation and how the money can be spent	Specifying budget plans for future calls

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<p>C.2.Develop common understanding</p>	<p>Unclear definition of roles/aims of communities & clusters.</p> <p>Unclear definition of community's organizational structures</p> <p>Overlaps between different work package deliverables</p>	<p>We must build a common mechanism or organizational structure for each EELISA community to handle administrative work (reporting, organizing joint meetings with member groups, etc..)</p>
<p>C.3.Participation</p>	<p>Encouraging partners to participate in events in person</p> <p>Stronger participation from professors at events</p> <p>Half of the universities are very active, but the other half do not participate in almost any event despite the facilities and financial aid. The reasons can be : Lack of information? A lot of work? Lack of enthusiasm or interest for the Alliance?</p> <p>Greater interaction between universities at the community level is essential. In other words, at a second level</p> <p>The increasing number of events decreases interest in them.</p> <p>It is difficult to enroll students, there are difficulties on the communication part, and delays too short sometimes.</p> <p>Despite funding, Researchers' communication and engagement is still a challenge</p>	<p>Implementing mechanisms to reward and incentivize participation can be beneficial in encouraging community members to engage in the calls actively.</p> <p>Mapping research topics/interests/problems in a very capillary way.</p> <p>Organizing meetings to share ideas, projects for activities, etc., to find and involve new partners</p> <p>Creating joint degree/master/Ph.D. programs or intensive blended programs to facilitate the participation of students in the activities</p> <p>In-depth study and analysis of barriers against equal participation by EELISA institutions.</p> <p>Help to contact professors and researchers with common interests from the other partner universities.</p> <p>Integrating the community activities directly to the curriculum by merging a community activity to a course program</p> <p>Fix one common week per semester to be free of other academic activities and to be dedicated to EELISA activities, e.g., taking advantage of the Athens Alliance (http://athensnetwork.eu/network-list.html)</p> <p>An online calendar of public events can help organizers decide the best event time.</p> <p>Best Practices of Partners to be leveraged:</p>

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	<p>Low level of interconnectedness between researchers, Lack of incentives =lack of motivation to build a community</p>	<p>UPM (InnoCORE) InnoCORE is developing and testing tools and instruments meant to boost research collaboration</p> <p>Lessons Learned and Best Practices of Communities:</p> <p>SSERIES enhanced the participation of some of its members in the two joint calls, also with new activities (e.g., with Research Based approaches), and enhanced the implementation of challenged based learning approaches in UPM courses (UPM call) and of a Citizen Lab, where any interested participant could propose a challenge to be solved in collaboration with other participants.</p> <p>OSC - The BLOOM-OS Bootcamp will boost early-career researchers' open science skills. Hopefully, it becomes a yearly event.</p>
C.4.Inclusivity	<p>Future Plans: what are the actions we are planning to increase the participation in SDGs that are less covered</p>	<p>The Egalitarian Societies Community has been significantly active and impactful through events connecting engineering with diversity, inequalities, etc.</p>
C.5. Sustainability - Continuity	<p>To follow and support the outputs obtained from the activities carried out until they are realized</p>	<p>The EELISA Connect workshops must have continuity: the results already obtained in the first wave of meetings need to be supported to continue with the development of the current proposals until their presentation.</p>

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Figure 3: Workshop on “Enabling EELISA Research & Innovation Strategy Through EELISA Communities” (Istanbul, July 12, 2023).

Future Directions

The workshop concluded with the future directions for EELISA Communities and their empowerment through the following actionable items. The future here refers to the short term, regarding EELISA Connect Workshops and the medium term regarding EELISA 2.0.

Motivation:

- Make the incentives visible:
 - The invisibility of incentives presents another challenge, especially for senior members. In this context, the motivation for participation in an EELISA community should be elaborated on since these motivation patterns enable participation and engagement.
- Move beyond self-motivation towards more robust motivation and incentives, recognizing that self-motivation alone may apply to a minority.
 - Motivation patterns of Communities are listed as a more extensive network, access to more resources, and Self-motivation. Build a clear understanding of how communities will contribute to the clusters. It must be communicated and defined practically, such as “Communities serve as problem finders (with a broader mission), while Clusters are problem solvers (thematic).

Multi-disciplinarity and Multi-focus

- Build a multidisciplinary scientific and technical approach in all communities to grow.
- Define actions to expand community coverage through SRAs and SDGs.

Engagement and Participation

- Engage all stakeholders, including researchers (professors), especially senior researchers, students, and staff.
 - **Solution (1):** Allocate sufficient time for student event preparation.

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- **Solution (2):** Support in-person participation by aligning academic calendars with the EELISA activity calendar.
- **Solutions (3):** Analyze and address issues related to the limited participation of students and professors in activities.
- **Solution (4):** Provide early notifications.

Governance:

- Assure transparency in EELISA processes.
- Explore any additional institutional barriers not mentioned that may hinder community effectiveness. Emphasize the importance of event participation, considering its impact on a participant's badge.
- Clarify credentials for both institutions and students, ensuring alignment with their respective grading systems. Without this alignment, it lacks coherence.

Communication:

- Establish connections among EELISA researchers working in the same areas, necessitating platforms and tools to facilitate researcher contact.
 - The lack of effective communication about events affects the number of participants, particularly regarding the engagement of separate activities/meetings under SRAs through the participation of young researchers (ECRs), supporting a bottom-up approach. The absence of an EELISA online event/activity calendar causes challenges in planning the involvement.
 - While some solutions/tools have been proposed, they are currently insufficient, necessitating detailed discussion.
- Enhance communication among partner institutions within the community.
- Discuss the collaboration with other alliances and networks (establishing linkages with other networks). Moreover, assess the current connections to determine specific needs.

Concluding Remarks on the Workshop:

In the D2.5 report and in the workshop presentation and discussions, it is also emphasized that the lack of a «Challenge Management System " in the EELISA innoCORE IT platform had been one of the challenges in the organizing and preparation process of D2.5.

The challenges mentioned in Symposia 1 on Communication, Coordination, and Engagement seem to have been overcome thanks to many improvements such as connect workshops, joint proposal calls, and academic position postings since Symposia 2, and they empowered the Communities and interactions. However, more robust information management procedures will be highly serving to leverage the impact of Communities on advancing the R&I dimension of EELISA.

For elaborating on the effectiveness of communities, it is essential to remember that the EELISA innoCORE strategy has a two-fold approach to the research and innovation dimension of the EELISA alliance, built on an ecosystem of horizontal and vertical structure as mentioned in The EELISA Portfolio of Clusters⁸: (1) The horizontal approach achieved through the EELISA communities created to transform the educational dimension of our alliance. These communities

⁸ EELISA INNOCORE Deliverable D5.2 EELISA's portfolio of Clusters (Date: 7 December 2022)

are oriented to face societal challenges that raise scientific and technological needs that researchers and innovators must address. (2) The vertical approach is achieved through the EELISA clusters, which are created when some researchers and innovators decide to develop joint actions to meet the scientific and technological needs of EELISA communities.

In this context, this report on D.2.3 intends to build a clear understanding of how communities will contribute to clusters. Hence, as mentioned in the sections above during the workshop, a challenge identified in Communities is the dualism between them and clusters preventing the clear definitions of communities in the R&I dimension. The roles and aims of communities and clusters still need to be better understood in the alliance. During the workshop, some practical definitions also occurred, such as “Communities serve as problem finders (with a broader mission), while Clusters are problem solvers”. In conclusion, we underline the “Motivation” dimension of the future directions to build a clear understanding of how communities will contribute to the clusters. Further practices and solutions in both physical and digital platforms towards this need should be supported.

We also note that the D2.5 report is already a living document to be updated following the progress in R&I activities in EELISA Communities. The content and conclusions from D2.5 were enhanced by the outputs from the discussions and recommendations in this workshop. Hence, this section of D2.3 on the outputs of “Enabling EELISA Research & Innovation Strategy through EELISA Communities Workshop” must be dealt as an annex to D2.5, complementing the findings of D2.3 based on the secondary data and the surveys with the insights from the panel.

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2. PANEL: JOINT INDUSTRIAL Ph.D. MODEL

The session on joint industrial Ph.D. took a place to understand the existing practices of each EELISA partner and the future directions on an EELISA joint Industrial Ph.D. framework including the key functions and activities required for the establishment, application, and management. The main objective of the panel was to assist partner institutions lacking such programs in adopting best practices from those already offering industrial Ph.D. opportunities.

The panel took place on 12 July 2023 at Istanbul Technical University Istanbul – Turkey, between 1.15 pm (CET time zone) and 3.00 pm (IST time zone) and lasted 105 minutes. A total of 20 participants attended the panel, which was held in a hybrid format, 15 of whom were physical.

In the first 50 minutes of the panel, the panelists presented the industrial Ph.D. practice at their institutions. After the presentations, in the remaining time, a moderated discussion followed with the topics below:

1. Please reflect on the good practices of locally arranged industrial Ph.D. at your institute. Reflect on success stories.
2. What is the local use of an industrial Ph.D. title, and in what terms is it different from the conventional one? What would be the use of an international one on the EELISA level?
3. What are the conditions of an industrial Ph.D. course at your institute and how do you see these on the international level among EELISA members?
4. Reflect on aspects to be improved regarding your institute's current industrial Ph.D. program.

Figure 4: Panel on “Joint Industrial Ph.D. Model” (Istanbul, July 12, 2023).

The names of the six panelists and their institutions can be seen below:

- Clarisse ANGELIER - Chief Executive Officer of the French National Association for Research and Technology (ANRT)
- Dr. Henriette MÜLLER-AHRNDT, Deputy Head of the FAU Graduate Centre
- Prof. Calogero ODDO, Professor at SSSA
- Sonia ROIG, Coordinator of doctoral programmes at UPM.
- Prof. Chiara CAPPELLI, Deputy Rector for Technology Transfer at SNS
- László Gergely Vigh – Director for International Academic Affairs, BME

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The panel has enhanced the understanding of each partner's existing status and practices regarding the Industrial Ph.D. programs. The main points revealed out from the panel can be seen below:

- There is no separate program for industrial Ph.D. for most EELISA partners as existing practices.
- Existence of an employment contract or commercial contract between the student and the company rather than a joint doctoral program between the university and the company.
- Industrial doctorate contracts funded by regional or national authorities in Madrid regarding UPM practices.
- "Cifre" (industrial research training agreements) are fully financed by the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation, which entrusts ANRT with implementing the program. French companies employ doctoral students and directly involve them in research partnerships with state laboratories.
- Arrangement on IP rights (IPR) between the company and university is very important.
- There are bilateral agreements with industrial partners with their R&D labs for BME with two supervisors (academic supervisor + industrial supervisor)

An industrial Ph.D. program involves collaborative research between universities and companies, providing students with valuable practical experience. By fostering cross-institutional learning and cooperation, it has been aspired to empower EELISA members to expand their industrial Ph.D. initiatives, thereby strengthening the union's commitment to cutting-edge research and industry-academia collaboration. In this panel, partner institutions that do not have industrial Ph.D. programs were enabled to listen to the best practices from institutions that currently offer industrial doctoral opportunities, and the steps to be taken to open a joint industry university doctoral program at the EELISA level in the future were discussed.

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3. PANEL: INDUSTRY CHAIR APPROACH

The industry chair approach panel took a place to discuss the Industry Chair among the EELISA partners for developing and executing a high-impact research agenda, developing multi-investigator programs and multi-disciplinary laboratories, developing innovative training programs and curricula, fostering collaborations across the industry and academia. An Industrial Chair, also known as an Industrial Research Chair or an Industrial Professorship, is a prestigious academic position that involves a close partnership between a university or research institution and an industry or a consortium of industrial partners.

The symposium panel discussion dedicated to exploring the diverse implementations of the Industrial Chair across EELISA partner universities has proven to be an invaluable platform for knowledge sharing and collaborative learning. By delving into the various models and practices adopted by our member institutions, we have gained profound insights into the multifaceted nature of the Industrial Chair role within our academic community. This session has underscored the importance of flexibility and adaptability in our nomination procedure, recognizing that different universities may have distinct yet equally effective approaches to fostering collaboration between academia and industry. The exchange of experiences and ideas has enriched our understanding of best practices and has undoubtedly contributed to the refinement and enhancement of our Industrial Chair nomination procedure. It is evident that this collaborative effort will further strengthen EELISA's commitment to advancing industry-academia partnerships for years to come.

The panel took place on 12 July 2023 at Istanbul Technical University Istanbul – Turkey, between 15.15 pm (CET time zone) and 17.00 pm (IST time zone) and lasted 105 minutes. A total of 23 participants attended the panel, which was held in hybrid format, 17 of whom were physical.

In the first 50 minutes of the panel, the panelists presented about the Industry Chair practices at their institutions. After the presentations, in the remaining time moderated discussion followed with the topics below:

1. What is the role, purpose, and task of an industrial chair at your university?
2. Please describe how an industrial chair is involved in academic evaluation processes at your university.
3. How does an industrial chair foster research cooperation between your university and the industry?
4. How can an industrial chair be involved in scientific research?
5. How is the industrial chair involved in the process of knowledge transfer?
6. What kind of system of financing does your university have for covering the tasks of an industrial professor?

Before the panel, the panelists reviewed the EELISA Industrial Chair Description as an attachment.

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Figure 5: Panel on “Industry Chair Approach” (Istanbul, July 12, 2023).

The name of six panelists and their institutions can be seen below;

- Juan Manuel MUÑOZ GUIJOSA, Associate Vice-Rector for Innovation and Technology Transfer- Director of the UPM Technology Transfer Office
- Alexandru MARIN, EU IPR Helpdesk Ambassador Director of the Technology Transfer Office at UPB
- Dr. Vincent SEMETÉY - CNRS Senior researcher at PSL - Head of Urban Mines Chair (ecosystem)
- Dr. Ayşe Aybike Şeker - Senior Lead Engineer at ASELSAN Academy
- Adrián Horváth - Industrial Professor at BME
- László Gergely Vigh – Director for International Academic Affairs, BME

Each participant from EELISA partners explained Industrial Research Chair status in their institutions. The important points emphasized in the panel can be seen below;

- Strategic, common benefit, based on trust and long-term collaboration are the important criteria regarding industry chair framework.
- Supporting mechanisms such as mentorship, labs and financial support are required in order to make industry -university collaboration sustainable.
- For EELISA Industry Chair Nomination criteria and execution rules, ACRI and/or Executive Board approval is needed.
- Instructing the lectures, participating in research work, consulting students for their thesis, mentoring the students at summer internship and being a jury member for Student Scientific Competition are the examples of some Industry Chair activities.

The workshop concluded with the future directions for EELISA Industry Chair approach with EELISA InnoCORE WP 6 (Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation) representatives' contributions.

The nomination and monitoring procedure for the EELISA Industrial Chair is a dynamic and inclusive framework that takes into consideration the diverse models of partner institutions within our consortium. The selection process should involve a thorough evaluation of candidates' portfolios, which may include individuals with diverse industry and academic backgrounds, or formal agreements between universities and companies. The Advisory Council for Research and Innovation (ACRI) leads the assessment to evaluate qualifications, collaboration potential, and commitment to diversity and inclusion.

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Following selection, the elected Industrial Chair will embark on a collaborative journey to foster research-based cooperation between academia and industry, with the primary goal of actively involving at least two EELISA partner institutions in their initiatives. Annual review meetings, and feedback mechanisms will ensure the Chair's performance aligns with the shared objectives.

The first EELISA Industrial Chair is expected to be elected by the end of 2023, marking a significant milestone in the EELISA InnoCORE Grant Agreement to advance industry-academia partnerships within the consortium.

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4. CONCLUSION

Regarding the workshop on Enabling EELISA R&I Strategy through EELISA Communities, some actionable needs are revealed. However, these issues also have some strategic and cultural dimensions. Transparency in EELISA processes must be guaranteed. EELISA members should be encouraged to participate in events and EELISA incentives should be made visible. Motivation patterns of communities should be reviewed, and motivational studies should be conducted accordingly. Tools and platforms should be developed to enhance research collaborations and to strengthen communication within and outside the Alliance. The interoperability of interconnected systems such as grading systems, curricula, laboratories, etc., owned by EELISA institutions, should be ensured. In short, a common understanding between all partners for EELISA is highly needed.

After the workshop the two fruit-full panels titled “Joint Industrial Ph.D. Model” and “Industry Chair Approach” were held respectively in the afternoon sessions in the II. Symposia with Representatives of R & I Structures. These two panels revealed some essential highlights on EELISA level on creating a space for discussion on developing and executing a high-impact research agenda, develop industry-investigator programs, multi-disciplinary laboratories, joint Industrial Ph.D. programs, innovative training programs and curricula through fostering collaborations across the industry and academia. In “Joint Industrial Ph. D Model” panel, partner institutions that do not have industrial Ph.D. programs were enabled to listen to the best practices from institutions that currently offer industrial doctoral opportunities, and the steps to be taken to open a joint industry university doctoral program at the EELISA level in the future were discussed. In addition; the diverse implementations of the Industrial Chair across EELISA partner universities has proven to be an invaluable platform for knowledge sharing and collaborative learning with the help of the Industrial Chair Panel. The exchange of experiences, best practices and ideas between panel participants has undoubtedly contributed to the refinement and enhancement of EELISA Industrial Chair nomination procedure.

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